

A Gamification Approach for Continuous Engagement in Engineering courses

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Abstract

This paper proposes an approach for continuous engagement in engineering courses using Kahoot! gamification. The main goal of the approach is increasing weekly interest in the course by providing regular assessment of the student progression in an entertaining and attractive way. For each different module of the course, a Kahoot! quiz is taken by the students to score several points proportional to the module length. The quiz includes basic questions on the topic. Points are only distributed among the top ten participants. At the end of the course, all points are summed to obtain the final classification. The course grade is increased up to 5% depending on the final position of the student. The experience aims at increasing the interest of the students and promote continuous learning from the beginning of the course. This paper describes the organization of the activities, the design of the Kahoot! quizzes, the tentative student survey to evaluate engagement and satisfaction and the quantitative assessment metrics of the proposed approach.

Keywords: Gamification; Active Learning; Engagement.

1 Introduction

Educational technology has been a matter of great importance in the last two decades, particularly in the STEM field (Chacko et al., 2015). The incorporation of alternative ways of promoting learning with current available technologies such as computer-based activities has been a priority of educational institutions. An example of this is the use of social networks such as Facebook to promote science education (Waghid, 2015) or open-source databases as Wikipedia (Meishar-Tal, H., 2015).

A very interactive way of promoting learning and engagement is gamification. This method tries to increase the student motivation by using game-thinking to solve problems (Conolly et al., 2012). Several studies have used gamification methods to increase engagement in students using a variety of platforms such as Knowingo (Welbers, et al., 2019), Class Dojo (DiGiacomo et al., 2022) or MinecrafEdu (Cózar-Gutiérrez and Sáez-López, 2016). A very simple and attractive option is the use of the Kahoot! platform. Kahoot! provides a series of learning games that include multiple-choice questions and puzzles. The use of Kahoot! gamification or similar systems has shown a significantly better performance in students' grades than those who had traditional teaching (Sarkar, Ford, & Manzo, 2017).

In this paper, we propose an approach for continuous engagement in engineering courses using Kahoot! gamification. The main goal of the approach is increasing weekly interest in the course by providing regular assessment of the student progression in an entertaining and attractive way. Some works have incorporated similar approaches to engineering courses including surveys and quantitative evaluation of certain parameters. These studies do not evaluate engagement elements and are more centered in the effect on final grades (Chernov et al., 2021) or in student satisfaction (Pertegal-Felices et al., 2020). For this reason, our proposal also includes possible metrics to evaluate how the gamification activities are affecting weekly engagement in the course contents and does not focus specifically in the effects on course performance.

This paper is divided as follows: in Section 2, the gamification methodology is explained including the structure of the activity, the design of quizzes, the scoring systems, the student survey and the evaluation metrics. Section 3 describes the possible additions to the gamification approach. Finally, Section 4 contains the conclusions.

2 Methods

In this section, we show the description of the structure of the gamification activities and the general and specific criteria to create the different quizzes. The satisfaction survey provided to the students at the end of the course is also described as well as the metrics extracted from the students' performance.

2.1 Structure of the activity

The gamification activity is divided into several quizzes (one per block) along the course, each of them with a set of 20 questions. Each course has specific characteristics and length, so the questions, distribution and score of quizzes are adapted accordingly (Figure 1). The activity is proposed for the following engineering courses in University of Alicante:

- **Service Robotics (BSc in Robotics Engineering):** This course describes the fundamentals of service robotics. A service robot is a robot that operates in a semi or totally autonomous way to provide useful services for the well-being of human beings or equipment, excluding manufacturing operations. The course is divided into 4 blocks with a Kahoot! quiz at the end of each. In a first block, the concept of human-robot interaction and the different methods available to carry it out are analyzed. In a second block, the main aspects of cognitive robotics are studied, including the analysis of cognitive architectures and cognitive human-robot interaction. The third block describes humanoid robots and aspects on locomotion of this type of robots. Finally, the last block presents the applications of service robotics in different areas, particularly centered in the use of robots for rehabilitation. Course length is divided into 15 theory lectures of 2 hours and 15 practical sessions of 2 hours (60 hours total).
- **Fundamentals of Systems and Instruments (BSc in Biomedical Engineering):** This course describes the use of systems and instrumentation in a clinical context. The course is divided into 4 blocks with a Kahoot! quiz at the end of each. In a first block, basic concepts of systems theory are introduced addressing possible clinical situations. A second block describes the main biomedical sensors used to measure human biosignals, including electroencephalography (EEG), electromyography (EMG), electrocardiography (ECG) and stimulation systems. The third block covers the application of robotics in clinical environments as for rehabilitation, assistance, surgery or motor substitution. Finally, the last block describes visualization systems in medicine and aspects of virtual and augmented reality for rehabilitation. Course length is divided into 15 theory lectures of 2 hours, 15 problem-case lectures of 1 hour and 10 practical sessions of 1 hour and 30 minutes (60 hours total).
- **Robot Control and Programming (MSc in Automation and Robotics):** This course is focused on the control and programming of robots in different environments. The course is divided into five different fields in robotics: rehabilitation robots, humanoids, robotic prostheses, space robotics and assistive robots. For each section a theoretical lecture is given followed by video examples of each topic and the Kahoot! quiz. Each section has a short introduction on the specific type of robot and aspects on how to interact and control them in practical applications. The practical contents are evaluated through a group project. Course length is divided into theory lectures up to 15 hours and 15 hours for the development of the practical project (30 hours total).

Service Robotics BSc in Robotics Engineering	Fundamentals of Systems and Instruments BSc in Biomedical Engineering	Robot Control and Programming MSc in Automation and Robotics
30% Quiz 1 – 10 questions <i>Human-Robot Interaction</i>	30% Quiz 1 – 10 questions <i>Biomedical Control Systems</i>	20% Quiz 1 – 10 questions <i>Rehabilitation Robots</i>
25% Quiz 2 – 10 questions <i>Cognitive Robotics</i>	20% Quiz 2 – 10 questions <i>Biomedical Sensors</i>	20% Quiz 2 – 10 questions <i>Humanoid Robots</i>
15% Quiz 3 – 10 questions <i>Humanoid Robots</i>	40% Quiz 3 – 10 questions <i>Medical Robots</i>	20% Quiz 3 – 10 questions <i>Robotic Prostheses</i>
30% Quiz 4 – 10 questions <i>Rehabilitation Robotics</i>	10% Quiz 4 – 10 questions <i>Biomedical Display Systems</i>	20% Quiz 4 – 10 questions <i>Space Robots</i>
		20% Quiz 5 – 10 questions <i>Assistive Robots</i>

Figure 1. Score ratio across modules for each of the courses where the methodology is or will be applied. The final score for the course is computed by multiplying quiz position by the score ratio of a particular module and summing up score for all course quizzes (score range: 0-100 points).

2.2 Design of quizzes

Kahoot! is a game-based learning platform used in educational institutions to promote additional ways of engaging students. Kahoot! provides a series of learning games that include a variety of questions such as multiple-choice, true and false, short answer, puzzles and audio questions. It also has the possibility of polling and brainstorming in a cooperative and intuitive way. Kahoot! can be accessed through a web browser or a smartphone app and allows the students to easily interact with the quiz from their seats in classroom.

For this educational experience we have proposed the use of only multiple-choice questions (4 options) to evaluate how students are following the weekly contents of each course. At the end of each block of contents, a series of 20 questions is presented to the students. Questions are divided into three categories:

- **Basic knowledge (B):** Includes basic concepts that should be known if the student has a minimal understanding of the contents of the block. This kind of questions are not expected to be included in final evaluation.
- **Advance knowledge (A):** Includes concepts that only students with a more detailed comprehension of the contents are able to know as they require a more complex reasoning. Questions of similar difficulty are included in the final evaluation.
- **Professor remarks (P):** Includes aspects that the professor has mentioned in class and that are not necessarily included in written content, i.e., slides or documentation.

A proposed question distribution for each Kahoot! quiz would be 10B, 5A and 5P questions. For quizzes that include a module with different submodules a proportional distribution of contents is advisable.

2.3 Scoring system

The proposed scoring system considers the length of each evaluated module as defined in Figure 1. For each quiz only the first 10 best students will score (10 to 1 point in descendent order). The score of the quiz will then be multiplied by the score ratio (proportion of the block divided by 10) and summed to the scores obtained in the other quizzes. The final score will give a maximum of 100 points. For example:

- If Student 1 from the Service Robotics course is 2nd in the first quiz, 6th in the second quiz, 14th in the third quiz and 10th in the fourth quiz, he/she will get a total score of $42.5 = 9 \cdot 3 + 5 \cdot 2.5 + 0 \cdot 1.5 + 1 \cdot 3$.
- If Student 2 from the Service Robotics course is 3rd in the first quiz, 4th in the second quiz, 5th in the third quiz and 1st in the fourth quiz, he/she will get a total score of $80.5 = 8 \cdot 3 + 7 \cdot 2.5 + 6 \cdot 1.5 + 10 \cdot 3$.

The final course grade is increased by a 5% if a student has the highest score of the whole course. Up to 10 students get an increase in the course grade. The student with the second highest score gets a 4.5% increase in the course grade and so on, until the 10th student who gets only a 0.5% increase in the course grade. This scoring system is intended to be proportional to the course contents and to reward not only the winner of each quiz but a fair number of students to avoid disengagement in the course of time. An additional prize for the winner can be optionally awarded. For engineering courses, we propose the 3D-printing of a trophy, medal or badge shaped in a course-related topic. This award is given to the winner by the end of the last quiz. This kind of reward is aimed at increasing the interest on this activity in the following academic years.

2.4 Student surveys

By the end of each course, students will answer to a questionnaire to evaluate aspects of engagement and satisfaction. Table 1 shows the proposed survey given to students. Each question follows a numerical Likert scale style from 1 to 10, being 1 "Strongly disagree" and 10 "Strongly agree".

Table 3. Elements of the student survey.

Type	Question
Engagement	Do you think the Kahoot!-based evaluation is a good tool to capture your interest in this course?
	Did your interest in the Kahoot!-based quizzes increased in time with each activity?
	Did this activity make you study in advance or have more interest in the contents to perform better in the quizzes?
	Did you have fun while doing this activity?
Satisfaction	Do you think the proposed Kahoot!-based evaluation is well balanced in terms of difficulty?
	Do you think the proposed Kahoot!-based evaluation is well balanced in terms of contents?
	Do you prefer this kind of activities instead of optional submissions of practical or theoretical exercises?
	Do you recommend doing this kind of activities in other courses?
	Do you think your position is fair compared to the effort you did?
	Do you think the score prize of this activity is high enough?
Do you agree with the scoring system?	
Short final answer	Do you have any suggestion to improve this activity?

2.5 Evaluation metrics

To evaluate the gamification in a quantitative way, several metrics are proposed:

Course scores

- *Average course final score*: this metric gives hints of the difficulty of quizzes for a particular group of students and can be compared to satisfaction questions from the student survey.
- *Average module correct questions*: this metric establishes which module has been more difficult for the students.
- *Average correct B questions*: this metric is useful to measure the general level of the group. B questions should be correctly answered by most of the students. If not, it could indicate a low level of competition or a proof of general disengagement.

- *Average correct A questions:* this metric is useful to measure if the lectures are of special interest to the students and how they have prepared for the quizzes.
- *Average correct P questions:* if high, this metric could indicate an especially relevant level of interest of the students to a particular course.

Fidelity

- *Number of students with all quizzes completed:* this metric establishes how many students did all the activities and shows if the gamification approach is interesting for the students.
- *Number of students completing each quiz:* together with score metrics, this parameter can help to determine if disengagement is due to difficulty and the loss of possibilities to win or is merely lack of interest.
- *Score progression of each student:* particularized to each student, this metric allows to study improvements in individual performance.
- *Average position of each student:* this metric allows evaluating how regular are students along the course.

3 Future developments

The gamification approach will be applied to the academic year 2022/2023. After evaluating the results, if positive, a pilot gamification approach will be proposed in combination with the Kahoot! quizzes in the course Robot Control and Programming within the MSc of Automation and Robotics. This course in particular is shorter than the other two and intensive, meaning that in only two weeks all the contents are given. Our proposal will include several elements to engage students:

- *Badge system:* we will incorporate a badge system to evaluate achievements during the course such as outstanding scores in specific theory and practical assignments or participation in class.
- *Video-based lectures:* in person lectures will be changed to video lectures and a flipped classroom approach will be introduced for the theory assignments.
- *Free-to-choose itinerary:* course modules will have a recommended order, but students will be free to choose which module order fits better their own interests.

4 Conclusion

This paper has described the organization of the activities, the design of the Kahoot! quizzes, the tentative student survey to evaluate engagement and satisfaction and the quantitative assessment metrics of a gamification approach to engineering courses. The main goal of this proposal is to evaluate how the gamification activities are affecting weekly engagement in the course contents and does not focus specifically in the effects on course performance. If the application of this approach is successful, more gamification elements are intended to be included in a pilot engineering course.

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